

Handling Editor pre-flight checklists

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Key resources:

- [Handling Editor resources directory on Google Drive](#)
- [Email templates](#)
- [Workflow diagram](#)
- [Handling Editor availability spreadsheet](#)

General tips

- Where possible, try to keep all contact with authors and reviewers inside the system using the internal **Discussion** mechanism, so that internal records are kept, and responsibilities can easily be picked up in case of re-assignment of roles.
- Authors won't be able to access/see **Discussions** thread in the Production tab.
- When drafting messages to authors or reviewers in OJS, there is no auto-save function, so make sure that you **regularly copy (ctrl-C) your draft text**. Alternatively, draft your text in a local application on your computer (e.g., MS Word).
- We have found issues with using OJS with **AdBlocker** software installed on computers / web browsers. If you find problems using the system, please check your browser settings first.
- **If you are away** for two weeks or more, and **unable to handle manuscripts** in this time, please give your unavailability using our [shared Calender](#) spreadsheet.

Where to find help and who to contact with questions/issues:

- Just ask on the Slack [#seismicaboard](#) channel to get the fastest response
- Editorial Assignments (for regular research articles and reports): [Gareth Funning](#) (Production Editor).
- Long-term availability/commitment for Seismica: [Christie Rowe](#) (Community Editor).
- Editorial workflow and best practices: [Stephen Hicks](#) (Handling Editor Liaison).
- Copyediting/production: [Hannah Mark](#) / [Thea Ragon](#) (Standards & Copyediting Chairs).
- Getting access to the reviewer database: [Martijn van der Ende](#) (Tech. Team co-Chair).
- Media & branding: [Jaime Convers](#) / [Ezgi Karasozen](#) (Media+branding team)

1. Initial post-submission checks

- Is there no [conflict of interest](#) between you and the authors?
 - If there is any potential conflict, please inform the Production Editor (via the Pre-Review Discussions area of the dashboard) who will be able to assign the submission to a different Handling Editor.
- Do you have the **time to commit** to handling this manuscript?
 - If not, please inform the Production Editor (via the Pre-Review Discussions area of the dashboard) who will be able to assign the submission to a different Handling Editor.
- Is the submitted **article type** appropriate?
 - The submitted article type can be viewed and changed in the Dashboard under the *Metadata* tab -> *Issue* -> *Section*.
 - If you decide to change, the authors should be informed (boilerplate email [here](#)).
- Is the manuscript in Seismica's [required format](#)? (e.g., 12-point font throughout, line numbers shown, double-spacing, figures contained within the main body of the paper).
- Ensure that the manuscript has **not been published elsewhere**, nor is it under consideration elsewhere.

If yes to all of the above, then select “**Send to Review**”.

2. Sending out for review

- Source two potential reviewers** (one for *Fast Reports*).
 - Reviewers can be found in [Seismica's reviewer database](#) (contact [Martijn van der Ende](#) if you need editor-level access).
 - Suggested reviewers from the authors will be in your editorial assignment discussion message from the Production Editor.
 - If no reviewers have been suggested by the authors, feel free to go back to the corresponding author and ask again.
- Check for no obvious **conflicts of interest** between the reviewers and authors.
- Invite no more than two reviewers at any one time
- Invite reviewers** by selecting 'Add Reviewer'.
 - Either: choose an existing reviewer from the internal database.
 - Or: select "Create New Reviewer" at the bottom of the pop-up window.
 - Review time limits are set by default to: 2 weeks to respond; 4 weeks to provide the review. These time limits should be changed manually for **Fast Reports**.
- Include detail about the reviewers' expertise in the invite message** - this helps with getting a positive response.
- For **Reports** or **Fast Reports**: the invitation message should be modified as appropriate (see boilerplate email directory for examples) to set expectations about different publication types.
- Introduce yourself** to the corresponding author as Handling Editor. A good time for this is once the first batch of reviewers has been invited. Try to do this within the "Review Discussions" section, but if you have any doubts over whether the corresponding author has received your message, then you should contact them via email.

Waiting for reviewers to respond:

- Automated reminder emails about sending review reports for confirmed reviewers will be sent by the system 3 days after the initial deadline (e.g., 4 weeks).
- There is no automated functionality to send a reminder email about the invitation. Reminders for overdue invitation responses can be sent using the 'Send Reminder' button.
- If a reviewer has not responded by the deadline, then they can be removed by selecting "Unassign Reviewer" after clicking on the small triangle next to the reviewer's name.
- If there are any delays, the corresponding author should be kept informed via *Review Discussions*.

3. Making a post-review decision

- Read each review** thoroughly & **ensure no abusive or libellous remarks/language**.
- Raise any case of suspected misconduct or disputed authorship with Seismica's Board.
- Internally **confirm receipt of each review** by clicking 'Review Details' and then clicking 'Confirm' at the bottom of each email.
- Select a decision** with "[Request Revisions](#)" / "[Accept Submission](#)" / "[Decline Submission](#)" buttons.
- Prepare your **decision letter**:
 - **Regardless of the exact decision, Editors should write an overall view, and summarise reviewer comments, rather than relying solely on the template message.**
 - Your decisions should be based on the peer reviews and your own view on the paper's importance, originality, clarity, validity, & relevance for Seismica.
 - If you are requesting revisions for the first time, then ensure the "*Revisions will not be subject to a new round of peer reviews*" button is selected in the pop-up window.
 - If you think that, once revisions are received, no further rounds of review will be necessary and the manuscript can be accepted, then you may want to request the author to upload all **manuscript source files** with their revised version. See [this pre-acceptance email](#) for an example.
 - Check again that manuscript has been submitted to the most appropriate section (e.g., Research Article, Reports, etc.).
 - If your decision is "Accept", then you will need to send certain files over to the copyediting stage. Therefore, all **manuscript source files** should be uploaded by the author before pressing "Accept". See [this pre-acceptance email](#) for an example.
 - To help our copyeditors, feel free to suggest minor style/grammar/spelling corrections.
 - Thank each reviewer** using the "Thank Reviewer" button.
 - At this stage, all reviewer reports and the editorial decision should be shared with all reviewers.
 - Provide clear advice and feedback to reviewers, where appropriate.
 - Editors can reduce reviewer fatigue and speed up the publication process by using their expertise to not send the manuscript to more rounds of review than necessary.

Pre-acceptance file and metadata checklist:

- The manuscript should be formatted with Seismica's templates (docx/odt/tex), and editable article files should be provided (including a .bib file if the tex template is used).
- All figures should be uploaded as separate files, in png or pdf format (dpi >= 300)
- Supplementary material should be uploaded as a separate file that will not be formatted. Supplementary material should not be included in the main paper.
- Most (>90%) references should contain DOI information.
- Reviewers should be recognised in the Acknowledgements.

- All author information is provided (ORCID, affiliation, contribution) and is coherent with the information entered at submission (OJS metadata).
- Data & code availability and reproducibility statements should be provided. Check that any Zenodo repository is linked to the Seismica community.

4. Copyediting/production stage

- Assign the paper to an **Issue** ('Publication' tab, then click on 'Issue').
- Assign **DOI** to paper ('Publication' tab, then click on 'Identifiers', then click 'Assign', then 'Save').
- Assign one of the **Standards and Copyediting** team Chairs to the manuscript (Hannah Mark or Thea Ragon).
 - When assigning, select the '[Seismica] Copyediting Request' template message.
 - In the assignment request, mention if there are any named reviewers and/or translators that should be credited on the first page of the published paper.
 - Report submitted and accepted dates.
 - Report Production Editor name
 - Report DOI
 - State clearly if a *Fast Report* submission.
- Assign one of the chairs of the **Media & Branding** team (Jaime Convers or Ezgi Karasözen), and specify if the paper is potentially newsworthy and may require a press release.
- Ensure that a PDF file containing **Review Reports** (and Replies) is included within the copy-editing workflow.
- Copy and Layout Editor will notify the Handling Editor that proofs are finalized and they are moving on to create the galleys
- Set a planned publication date** with the Copy+Layout Editor (might require extra time for complex papers) and M+B members, and notify the corresponding author. Default publication date: 7 days after proof validation, 3 days for Fast reports.
- Handling Editor makes **final pre-publication checks** (see list below).
- On the publication date, Handling Editor publishes the manuscript by clicking "**Schedule for publication**" on the top-right and then clicking "ok."
 - Be sure to notify one of the S&CE chairs (Hannah Mark or Théa Ragon) when the paper is published so they can deposit the DOI with CrossRef. The production editor (Gareth Funning), the HE liaison (Steve Hicks), and others who manage the OJS site (tech team) are also able to help with this as needed.
- Notify the corresponding author and the reviewers that the paper is published (there is currently no functionality to support an automated email for this).
- DO NOT advance the manuscript to the *Production* stage.

Final pre-publication checks:

- Use the 'Preview' tool (upper right corner) to check the manuscript webpage and the final PDF

and XML galleys.

- Review Reports (and Replies) should be uploaded as galleys.
- DOI in the final PDF galley should be correct.
- Authors (names and affiliations) listed in the OJS '*Contributors*' tab should correspond to contributors listed in the PDF and XML galley
 - In the '*Publication*' tab, go to '*Contributors*', select each author, click '*Edit*', then click '*Save*'
- Authors may need to be reminded to link their ORCIDs:
 - In the '*Publication*' tab, go to '*Contributors*', select each author, click '*Edit*', then tick the box '*Send e-mail to request ORCID authorization from contributor*' then click '*Save*'. Manually filling in the "*homepage URL field*" with ORCID ids **will not link** the ORCID id.
- Title & abstract given in the '*Title and Abstract*' tab should match the title & abstract in the PDF galley.
- References should be listed in plain text in the OJS references tab.
- Check that the correct Section has been assigned (publication tab -> issue).